

Abstract

Phyto-Acupuncture: Cannabis-Derived Cannabinoids and Opioid Pathways in the Management of Neuropathic Pain, Neurodegenerative, and Metabolic Diseases.

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Background: Acupuncture is an established therapeutic technique involving the percutaneous stimulation of neural structures to influence sensory, motor, and autonomic pathways via neuromodulation. When integrated with electrical stimulation, acupuncture enhances the release of endogenous opioids and regulates somato-visceral reflex homeostasis, thereby potentiating its analgesic efficacy.

The Endocannabinoid System (ECS): The ECS serves as a fundamental regulatory network governing neuroprotection, inflammation, immunity, pain modulation, and metabolism. Cannabinoids—comprising endocannabinoids, phytocannabinoids derived from *Cannabis sativa L.*, and synthetic analogues—interact with ECS components primarily through Cannabinoid Receptors 1 (CB1R) and 2 (CB2R). While Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) provides psychotropic and analgesic properties, Cannabidiol (CBD) is non-intoxicating and exerts potent anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects.

Synergistic Mechanisms: Current evidence suggests a bidirectional interaction between acupuncture and the ECS. Acupuncture has been shown to stimulate endocannabinoid release and up-regulate the expression of CB1R and CB2R, both of which are critical to its antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. The concurrent application of acupuncture and phytocannabinoids (including CBD, THC, and terpenes) may enhance therapeutic outcomes while minimising potential adverse effects.

Clinical Implications: Cannabinoids contribute to neuroprotection by modulating microglial activation, reducing protein aggregation, and stimulating neurogenesis. Furthermore, they improve metabolic function by decreasing visceral adiposity, enhancing insulin sensitivity, and suppressing systemic inflammation.

Conclusion: The synergistic relationship between acupuncture and cannabinoids represents a promising multimodal strategy for managing chronic pain, neuroinflammatory conditions, and metabolic disorders through complementary neuromodulatory and homeostatic pathways.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Cannabinoids; Endocannabinoid System (ECS); Neuropathic Pain; Neuroinflammation; Metabolic Syndrome.

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